

NANOCOMPOSITE ZEOLITE GRANULES AS SOIL AMENDMENT: SYNTHESIS, CHARACTERIZATION AND HEAVY METAL STABILIZATION

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The intensification of human activities has resulted in higher concentrations of heavy metals in the environment, including soils, thereby increasing the likelihood of these metals entering the food chain. Chemical stabilization/solidification using mineral amendments derived from reactive minerals and organic materials is considered a highly promising modern technique for soil remediation. This method reduces the bioavailability of heavy metals (HM) by transforming contaminants into less soluble or mobile forms.

Zeolites are considered effective amendments for HM stabilization in soils. However, the reversible nature of ion exchange processes involving zeolites requires their modification to improve contaminant fixation. One approach is to introduce additional functional groups on the zeolite surface, that can form strong complexes with heavy metal ions.

This study explores the synthesis and application of composite zeolite granules coated with hydrated iron (III) oxide nanoparticles as an efficient soil amendment for the stabilization of heavy metals/metalloids, including cadmium, lead, zinc, copper and arsenic. The zeolite granules were prepared by a controlled coating process in which hydrated iron (III) oxide nanoparticles were deposited onto the zeolite matrix (clinoptilolite tuff, Sokirnitsya deposit, Ukraine) to enhance the contaminant binding capacity. The granules were characterized using a range of analytical techniques, including scanning electron microscopy (SEM), X-ray diffraction (XRD) and BET surface area analysis, which confirmed the successful incorporation of the nanoparticles and the structural integrity of the composites.

Subsequent experiments evaluated the effectiveness of the composite zeolite granules in stabilizing heavy metals in contaminated soil (Příbram, Czech Republic). The results showed that the composite zeolite granules effectively reduced the concentration of cadmium, lead, zinc, copper in the soil, significantly reducing the bioavailability and mobility of mentioned heavy metals. The improved metal stabilization was attributed to the high surface area and reactive sites provided by the iron nanoparticles, which facilitated stronger HM interactions.

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